

CREATIVE APPROACH TO FORMING A CULTURE OF LEARNING IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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The love of reading books first of all starts from the family, parents should become readers themselves in order to instill a love of reading in their children

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The book, which is recognized as the eighth miracle, is a true companion of the human heart, mind and thoughts. Do you know when and what the oldest books were made of? The first books on earth were made of clay in ancient Assyria and Babylon. In ancient Egypt, book texts were written on stone tablets.

In our country, under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, large-scale reforms are being carried out in the direction of increasing and promoting book reading and reading culture. After all, "the book is the most unique discovery of humanity that lifts us from the earth to the sky, leads us to perfection, enlightens the soul, teaches us to distinguish between white and black, good and evil," says the head of our state.

On January 12, 2017, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of a commission on the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, increasing and promoting book reading and reading culture" was adopted. In this order, it is necessary to attract a large segment of the population to reading books, to widely promote reading and reading, to raise our children to be fond of books from the kindergarten age, to pay attention to the content of book products, and to improve the quality of their printing. and ensuring that it reaches remote villages and farms, increasing the number of bookstores filled with books of various contents, paying special attention to enriching the library fund, promoting the published books among the population on the basis of mass media - it is planned to pay special attention to the organization of advertisements, raising interest and holding various contests among active librarians and promoters in this process.[1]

We live in an age of rapidly developing civilization. There are so many ideas and thoughts that can quickly affect the thinking of people, that it will not be easy for us to "digest" them. Good books are the kindest teachers who say good things.

[2]

In this sense, raising the culture of reading, improving the skills in this regard, widely promoting noble concepts such as "Family reading", "One book for one

child", "Let's share a book" is one of the important factors determining the development of society.

Through their performances, the guests of the event showed that it is necessary to love the book as a source of knowledge, to be able to choose it and to know the culture of reading, to pay special attention to the enrichment of the library, the etiquette of keeping books, the reading process, reading what is read. They recognized that it is the culture of reading to apply to oneself and one's life.

Our President Shavkat Mirziyoev's insightful thoughts about books and reading excited everyone. This is a very urgent issue. Besides, our first president, Islam Karimov, taught my youth to love books at a high level and the culture of reading. Because it is not a pillow, but books on the blessed head of a person, the fact that books are a pillow for that person does not make any heart flutter. [3]

Hazrat Navoi's ghazals, written at the age of five, are kept as the most unique exhibits in St. Petersburg museums. This will certainly make every Uzbek, compatriot, proud. If we look at the lives and works of all scientists and scholars who have literally taken a place in the hearts of our people, people who have achieved high results, the service and contribution of the books they read is incomparable.

Reading enriches the spiritual world of all of us, improves our conversational culture. In some cases, it is necessary to read a book in order to prevent some of our compatriots from becoming rude and poor due to the "service" of our sacred Uzbek language. However, our Uzbek language is one of the richest languages in the world. A.S. Pushkin used a total of 21,197 words throughout his work, while the language of Shakespeare's works used a total of more than 20,000 words. Spanish scientists reported that 18,000 words were used in Cervantes' work. The number of words used in the works of our great grandfather Alisher Navoi is more than 26,000. (Kadirov P. Til et al.-Tashkent, 2010, page 127). It is necessary to read books to preserve our national wealth. In fact, increasing reading culture is the need of the hour.

One of the 12 smallest books in the world was a miniature version of the Holy Quran, and another was the Constitution of France. Books, big or small, are great musicians capable of touching the most delicate strings of the human heart. Once upon a time, people used to gather together in long winter nights, put their feet on warm sandals and listen to the great poet like a book. They took its content to their hearts. Maybe that's why they survived the pain of the hard years... [4]

Book therapy. You know, it has been a long time since an unusual profession - book therapist specialty - was established in Britain. In this field, there are

specialists working on the basis of the program of attracting people who are surrounded by mental problems to books. For example, Francis Scott Fitzgerald's "The Great Gatsby", Sol Bellow's "Hendersen - The Rain King", and Iris Murdoch's "The Bell" are recommended for diagnosing a middle-aged person worried about the economic crisis. And ladies are advised to present the book "The Time Traveler's Wife" by Audrey Niffenegger and "Jazz Tunes" by Tom Robbins to their friend who is getting married.

We need books that are a companion of the most difficult and sad years, to be with us in today's bright days - from the father of the family to the smallest child! Georgian brides will definitely have a book by Shota Rustaveli in their dowry. This is a really high value. It would be appropriate if we also follow such values and traditions of "one book per child" and introduce the tradition of giving books instead of expensive gifts on our birthdays.[5]

"A nation that does not know its history and has forgotten its past has no future," wrote Islam Karimov, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in his work "High spirituality is an invincible power".

Uzbekistan has been carefully preserving for the next generation the masterpieces of its centuries-old culture, the scientific and literary heritage of its world-famous scholars, including their unique books, popularizing it among the younger generation.

Indeed, the book is a source of knowledge. And reading a book is an honorable work that rewards a person throughout his life. In this regard, the family plays an important role in instilling a love of reading in children. Let's try to instill a love of books in our children. Let's not forget that the book has a great influence on us and gives us a very deep life experience.

Speaking of books, I remembered an incident that happened on a train in the 80s of the last century:

A student from Khorezm, nicknamed "Ghulam Khalta" by his classmates, goes home by train carrying two full bags. His cargo does not go unnoticed by the train controllers. The supervisors come and demand Ghulam to open the bag. His reluctance to open the bag increases the suspicion of the supervisors and they order Ghulam to open the bag immediately. Desperate, our hero opens the bags. Ghulam's only treasure, his treasured treasure, was the old books from the old library. On another matter, one of the supervisors, who wanted to catch Ghulam, put his finger on the edge, gave the "crazy, stupid" sign and whistled away...

Today, book lovers like Ghulam are recognized not as "book fanatics", but as "cultured readers", which also determines the level of people's culture and spirituality. [6]

Not only in families and educational institutions, but also in organizations, conducting "Mushoiras Nights" leads people to the distant destinations of the world of fantasy, and the beautiful verses that evoke special warm feelings in the hearts attract others and bring them into the world of poetry. [7]

It is known that every teacher needs to find the most advanced and effective methods to achieve the goal of the lesson. The more reading lessons in primary education are based on news, the more students' interest in science and reading works of art will increase. It should be noted that reading lessons are the best reading lessons for students. In this case, it is important for the teacher to properly organize the lesson and use various methods of education, to increase the activity of students in the classroom, to instill good qualities in them, and to use various methods to interest the student in reading books. [8]

It should be mentioned separately that the teacher, first of all, reads a small annotation about the work of art to the students, and on the basis of this, offers an approximate condemnation of the series of events in the work. After the drafts are ready, they are read out by the students and compared with what the writer wants to say.

Thomas Edison said, "Creativity is an involuntary process." But every day many experts feel the need to find unusual solutions to problems. Can they make this involuntary process voluntary? In this regard, it is important to develop students' creative thinking through more different types of task work. [9]

A sufficiently creative reading culture can be formed among students through the role-playing games "Extra image", "Think and search, find - it's you", "I am a reader" and "Write a small annotation about the work".

In addition, in order to increase students' interest in books in the role-playing game "I am a bookworm", keeping a "Bookworm's diary" and writing comments on the works they read will have a positive effect on their creative ability. In order to increase the interest of the students in reading the artistic ages, the teacher presents the audio and android versions of the books through social networks, which also gives the expected result. [10]

A discerning reader tries to find a suitable solution to real-life problems by reading a work of fiction, and sometimes finds it. It is impossible for a person who has not developed reading skills to think. It is also true that when people stop reading, they stop thinking. In particular, there will be no development in

the society as long as there is no transition from abstract thinking to live observation. The only solution to achieving a developed society is to be able to form and develop a culture of creative reading by members of society in all aspects of social life, not only in educational institutions.

References:

1. “Kitob va kitobxonlik – inson ma’naviyati ko’zgusi” internet ma’lumotlari <http://www.uzdon.uz/uz/news/info/events/873/>
2. Тўрақулова.О, Adabiyot darslarida mutolaa madaniyatini rivojlantirishga doir, “Замонавий таълим” журнали, 23-24-б.
3. Hayitova F.A. “Kitobxonlik – millat ko’zgusi”, Respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyalar to’plami, Samarqand, 2018.
4. Hayitova, F. . (2022). Kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishda sinfdan tashqari ishlarning o’rni. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(8), 235–242. извлечено от <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/3512>
5. Abdullaevna H. F., Doniyorovna R. M. Requirements for the formation of reading culture //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). – 2020. – Т. 9. – №. 5. – С. 240-245.
6. Хайитова Ф. А., Хуррамов Х. М. У. Педагогические идеи мыслителей о профессии учителя в обществе //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2019. – №. 6-1 (41). – С. 80-82.
7. Хайитова Ф. А., Хуррамов Х. М. У. Значение национальных ценностей в воспитании молодежи //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 1 (42). – С. 88-95.
8. Abdullaevna H. F., Menglimamat P. J. The importance of forming a reading culture in the process of extracurricular activities //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 12.
9. Abdullaevna H. F., Menglimamat P. J. The importance of extracurricular work in the cultivation of creative abilities of students in primary schools //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 12.
10. Ҳайитова Ф. А. и др. Важность использования рисунков при описании текста работы на уроках начального класса //Фундаментальные основы инновационного развития науки и образования. – 2018. – С. 38-41.

